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ABSTRACTS

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In-Silico Analysis of Bacteriocin against Anti-Microbial Resistance Proteins

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Abstract: MRSA, or Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, is a strain of bacteria that has developed resistance to many antibiotics and is a significant cause of difficult-to-treat infections in humans. The resistance of gram negative bacteria to antimicrobials stands as a significant global health concern. Consequently, diverse strategies have been recently investigated for their treatment, among which the research on bacteriocins is noteworthy. Bacteriocins, a class of peptides synthesized by bacteria, exhibit efficacy in managing clinically relevant susceptible and drug-resistant bacteria. The present study aims to carry out in-silico analysis between bacteriocins and Anti-Microbial Resistance (AMR) proteins like Nor, A efflux pump (PDB id: 7LO7), *Staphylococcus aureus* Protein A (PDB id: 1BDD) and Penicillin Binding Protein 2A (PDB id: 5M19). In the protein-protein docking analysis involving 105 bacteriocins and AMR proteins, Listeriocin and Acidocin A exhibited the highest docking scores among the candidates. Molecular docking and molecular dynamics outcomes further revealed a stable interaction between Listeriocin and Acidocin A with Penicillin Binding Protein 2A (PDB id: 5M19). This underscores the promising potential of bacteriocins as an alternative avenue in antimicrobial studies for therapeutic interventions.

Keywords: Antimicrobial Resistance, insilico analysis, bacteriocins, molecular docking, molecular dynamics.

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